

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KYENDREBEOGO****FIRST NAME: JESSICA****PROGRAM CODE: MBIAO****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not*-use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not*-use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1

1) INTRODUCTION

Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack period one* (EUCLID 2019) is a comprehensive manual of academic writing standards. Its nine chapters provide the procedures for a good academic writing such as essay writing which is without evidence the foundation of all graduate studies. This response paper will focus on the five first chapters of the coursepack namely essay writing basics, plagiarism, some rules of thumbs for writing papers, literature review and what is a style guide and why would I need one.

2) THE BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING

The first key concept deals with the basics of essay writing. To write a good academic essay, I must start doing an upstream work in order to understand the topic. The first action is to define the keys words and analyze the topic. Then I must organize my ideas and arguments to be able to draft a plan. “You can’t write successful essay unless you give yourself enough time to read, research, think and write” (EUCLID 2019, 1). While reading, it is necessary to make notes using arguments and bibliographic references. Then will come up the answers I am looking for.

After having my research done and gathering ideas, I must give a structure to my essay. An essay is composed of an introduction, a body and a conclusion that correlate with my ideas.

An introduction moves from global to specific overview. It brings up the topic, includes the answer to the question and provides a brief summary of the thesis statement. The body of an essay is a set of paragraphs. Each paragraph with a main point is explanatory and supported by evidence, examples from our research. The conclusion moves from specific to general. It is necessary to remind in few sentences our answers to the question, recap the main points and open perspectives. The period one coursepack recommends to “structure your essay to communicate your ideas and answer the question” (EUCLID 2019, 3).

When I write essays, references are an absolute prerequisite to support my ideas. I must use them according to the styles specified by my Faculty. “All academic essays MUST contain references. Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offence” (EUCLID 2019, 4).

3) PLAGIARISM

Basically, plagiarism means taking ideas or words from a source without giving credit (acknowledgement) to the author (Stephen Bailey 2011, 30). It is a serious academic offence. The source can be a text, data, quotation, article, or graph. To avoid plagiarism, I must always cite the sources of someone else’s information or use my own words to reproduce the accurate information of an author.

The period one coursepack teaches us that there are different ways of citing sources by in-text citation, quotation, and paraphrase. An in-text citation “refers to citing the piece of work you are using within the actual text itself” (EUCLID 2019, 6). Using a quotation means bringing the original words of a writer into your work. Paraphrase is a “re-writing of a text with substantially different wording and organization but similar ideas” (Bailey 2011, 310).

4) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

The period one coursepack listed some important of rules of thumb to be followed starting with main thesis.

It is mentioned in the chapter three the following: “state the main thesis of your paper (or near) the beginning: preferably in the opening paragraph” (EUCLID 2019, 14).

It is important to stay focused when we are writing and describe the relevant aspects of the assed theory. Another fact is to stick to these aspects to avoid being off topic.

Another paragraph of the coursepack says that a good paper is written with short, clear and simple sentences. The sections must have connections between them as we make transitions. The use of words and styles should make the reading of my paper interesting and not boring.

When a passage plays an important role in a paper, I can include it in my essay by using or not quotations.

It is said in the coursepack that I must treat an author's subjects as seriously as possible because they are the result of long and relevant research work: "the authors often distributed drafts of their manuscripts to other people, and then tried to incorporate responses to the objections they received" (EUCLID 2019, 16).

In the chapter, I also learned that I could use the first person singular, the "I" in my papers.

As a reminder, any idea taken from a source must be footnoted; otherwise we are in plagiarism subject to sanctions: "Second, you plagiarize if you take ideas from a source without footnoting the source. Sanctions for plagiarism depend on its severity and may range from lower grades on an assignment to a failing grade for the course" (EUCLID 2019, 16).

5) LITTERATURE REVIEW

In the chapter four of the period one coursepack, 11 important reminders are highlighted supported by examples. These are among others the use of commas, the apostrophe followed by "s", the use of proper punctuation, the subject and verb, the active voice, the period and the possession, the use of numbers in a text.

These aim to remind students to rule to write correct sentences. As an example: "Use the commas to bracket nonrestrictive phrases, which are not essential to the sentence's meaning" (EUCLID 2019, 17) or "Make the subject and verb agree with each other, not with a word that comes between them" (EUCLID 2019, 17).

Further, the chapter four of the coursepack reminds the rules of the use of "I" versus "me." This is very interesting since myself I am confused when using them.

6) WHAT IS A STYLE GUIDE AND WHY WOULD I NEED ONE?

The chapter five of the coursepack teaches us the necessity to follow a style. A style is recommended depending on the type of writing we are doing. A style guide is defined in the coursepack as "a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent" (EUCLID 2019, 24). It is important to know which style is used in our academic writing. In my case, EUCLID recommends the Chicago rules (Turabian) and the use of American English.

Writing is not just the standard use of grammar or punctuation. It implies taking into account different aspects. Depending on the field, a specific style must be considered.

7) **CONCLUSION**

ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack period one reviews the academic and international writing techniques. The topics addressed with examples provided have helped me learn the basics to international academic writing, the use of styles and rules to apply. I find the coursepack very useful and I will practice what I have learned throughout my studies.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Bailey, Stephen. 3rd ed. 2011. *Academic Writing, a Handbook for International Students*. London and New York. Routledge.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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